

Lymph Node Cytopathology Redefined: A Study on the Efficacy of the Sydney System

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Abstract:

Introduction: Lymph node fine needle aspiration Cytology (FNAC) is a useful diagnostic tool in the initial evaluation of lymphadenopathy of unknown etiology. The new Sydney System (2020) for classification and reporting of lymph node FNAC has put forth guidelines for a categorical classification using uniform terminology and morphologic criteria, a major step towards standardization for unified reporting language among cytopathologists and clinicians.

Aim: The study was aimed to evaluate cytopathology of lymph node lesions by applying the proposed Sydney system and to assess the category wise Risk of Malignancy (ROM) by comparing with histopathology diagnosis in available cases. The present study aimed to analyze the utility of the proposed system in cytopathology reporting in our institution.

Materials and Methods: This is a retrospective observational study, conducted from Aug 2022 to May 2024, on lymph node aspirates obtained in the department of Pathology of a tertiary care hospital. FNAC of 75 lymph node aspirates were evaluated. Smears were reviewed and categorized as per the Sydney System of reporting as, L1: non-diagnostic/inadequate, L2: benign, L3: atypical cells/atypical lymphoid cells of undetermined significance, L4: suspicious for malignancy, L5: malignant. The diagnostic accuracy of cytology and ROM in each category was assessed comparing with the gold standard histopathology diagnosis where available. This study has been undertaken to investigate the different lymph node cytopathology by the use of fine-needle aspiration cytology (FNAC). To standardize the FNAC results Sydney System of classifying and reporting was used.

Results: This is a retrospective study carried out from Aug 2022 to May 2024 at a tertiary care hospital. A total of 75 patients between 1 month to 99 years of age were included. Male preponderance was found. Commonest group of LN involved was cervical group. According to Sydney system LN cytology cases were categorized into L1: inadequate/nondiagnostic (09), L2: benign (52), L3: atypical cells of undetermined significance/atypical lymphoid cells of uncertain significance (02), L4: suspicious (03) and L5: malignant (09).

Conclusion: The Sydney system of structured reporting in lymph node cytology provides a clear-cut terminology, uniformity, and reproducibility of reports. It enhances the role of FNAC by alerting the clinician for follow-up and ancillary studies in atypical and equivocal cases. The Sydney system is an excellent system for accurately categorizing lymph node aspirates with greater reproducibility of reports and better patient management through improved communication between cytopathologist and clinician.

Keywords: lymph node pathology, FNAC, Giemsa stain.

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Introduction

Fine-needle aspiration cytology (FNAC) of lymph nodes (LNs) is a powerful tool to diagnose specific infections and nonspecific inflammatory processes and metastases, but its use in diagnosing lymphoid proliferations and lymphomas remains one of the most controversial areas in the application of FNAC cytopathology. Although lymph node FNAC has been performed for more than 60 years in both general and tertiary academic teaching hospitals, there are still different opinions and levels of acceptance

among clinicians, hematopathologists and cytopathologists in its ability to diagnose lymphomas [1]. Lymph nodes (LN) are among the most common sites targeted by FNAC. In both the adult and pediatric setting, LN-FNAC can assess whether lymphadenopathy (LAP) is benign or malignant and provide staging information in patients with an established diagnosis of malignancy. LN-FNAC can be performed to relieve anxiety and provide material

for microbial cultures and reduce unnecessary surgery. The main difficulties and limitations of LN FNAC are due mainly to the large number of complex neoplastic and non-neoplastic lymphoid processes and lesions that involve lymph nodes, as well as the lack of guidelines for LN FNAB performance, interpretation of diagnostic cytopathological criteria, categorization and reporting [2]. Furthermore, lymphoproliferative processes can also be detected on FNAC in extra nodal locations where the same diagnostic challenges may arise [3-8]. However, taking into account the wide spectrum and complexity of pathology presenting in LN [3], the resulting cytopathology, and required ancillary techniques, a simple classification system similar to those used for the thyroid gland, urine, or salivary gland FNAC is not adequate for LN-FNAC. At the same time, the clinical contexts and indications to perform LN-FNAC vary greatly and the technical procedures and testing are not equally available in different institutions and different countries.

In this setting, after an intense online exchange of views and opinions, a steering committee of international cytopathologists involved in LN-FNAC met at the International Cytology Congress in May 2019 in Sydney, Australia, and decided to develop a system for reporting LN-FNAC. This proposed system, integrates clinical and imaging information with key diagnostic cytopathological features and ancillary techniques, and is linked to a management algorithm, including options, which reflects the varying medical infrastructure available internationally. There are five diagnostic categories, namely, L1 to L5, denoting nondiagnostic, benign, atypical cells of undetermined significance, suspicious of malignancy, and malignant, respectively. It also provides recommendations for management in each category. There are studies in the literature that had analyzed the utility of this system in routine reporting [9-14].

The present study aimed to analyze and classify lymph node pathology as per new proposed Sydney system for reporting lymph node cytopathology & establish the histopathological correlation of each category, and highlight the cytological features of rare and atypical lymphoid lesions. Its application helps to screen infectious diseases and to differentiate between benign and malignant conditions.

Method

Table 1: Diagnostic categories as per the Sydney system.

S.N	Category	Criteria
1	Category I/L1	Inadequate/Non-diagnostic Blood only, Necrosis
2	Category II/ L2	Benign, Acute lymphadenitis, Reactive hyperplasia, Granulomatous lymphadenitis, Necrotizing granulomatous lymphadenitis
3	Category III/L3	Atypical non-lymphoid cell, Atypical lymphoid cell
4	Category IV/L4	Atypical cells of undetermined significance, Suspicious for malignancy
5	Category V/L5	Malignant, Metastatic squamous cell carcinoma, Metastatic adenocarcinoma, Metastatic breast carcinoma, Metastatic small cell carcinoma, Metastatic mel-

Study Design: The present study was a retrospective & observational analysis of lymph node aspirates obtained during one and half year period from Aug 2022 till May 2024, done in the department of pathology of a tertiary care centre. The study was approved by the Institutional Ethical Committee. All statistical analysis was done using SPSS.

Inclusion Criteria: FNAC of 75 patients of all ages presented with lymphadenopathy during the study period for which subsequent histopathological examination reports or clinical follow-up data were available, were included in the study.

Exclusion Criteria: Cases without corresponding histopathological correlation and loss to follow-up cases for subsequent clinical data were excluded from the study.

Cytological Samples: In all cases, FNAC was conducted by experienced cytopathologists and under ultrasonography guidance as and when needed, such as in cases of deep-seated or suspected malignant lymph nodes. An explanation of the procedure to the patient along with its possible risks and benefits. Was given. A 23G needle was used to conduct the procedure, and direct smears were prepared from the first pass. Some of the smears were subjected to rapid on-site evaluation (ROSE) by using Diff Quik stain to evaluate for adequacy. In case of smears that yielded scant material, a second pass was performed. The smears were stained by using both May Grünwald and Giemsa, and Papanicolaou stains. Special stains, such as Ziehl-Neelsen staining for acid fast bacilli was done for suspected tuberculosis cases. Cell block preparations were processed for bloody samples. Diagnosis of lesions was made based on specific morphological patterns and as per standard cytological guidelines [15]. Immunophenotyping and cell block preparation were carried out for selected cases as recommended.

Result

A total of 75 aspirates of lymphadenopathy were analysed. In the present study the age of patients varied from 1 year to 90 years with a mean age of 31.24 years. The most common age group undergoing LN FNAC in the study was age 21 to 50 years group. The gender ratio in the study was 1.09:1 for male to female. Commonest group of LN involved was cervical group, followed by axillary and inguinal nodes.

	anoma, Metastatic poorly differentiated carcinoma, Metastatic thyroid carcinoma, Non- Hodgkin's lymphoma, Hodgkin's lymphoma Leukemia infiltration, Burkitt lymphoma
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Table 2: This tables shows that the maximum no. of cases lies in between 21 to 50 years of age group.

Age in Years	No. of Cases
1-10	02
11-20	08
21-30	10
31-40	23
41-50	12
51-60	10
61-70	07
71-80	02
81-90	01
Total	75

Table 3: shows the distribution of cases registered according to the Sydney system of classification

S.N	Category	Percentage of cases
1	Category I/L1	11.6%
2	Category II/ L2	68.9%
3	Category III/L3	2.7%
4	Category IV/L4	3.9%
5	Category V/L5	12.9%

Table 3 shows that the most common cytological diagnosis in our study was reactive hyperplasia of lymph node. The most common malignant lesion diagnosed on cytology in our study was metastatic squamous cell carcinoma. The findings of the present study are in accordance with the study of Joshee A et al. [16]

Table 4: Details of FNAC cases with cytological diagnosis

SN	Category	Cytological Diagnosis	No. of Cases	Total No. of cases
1	L1- Inadequate/ Non diagnostic	Blood only	05	09
		Necrosis	04	
2	L2- Benign	Reactive Lymphadenitis	29	52
		Granulomatous Lymphadenitis	23	
3	L3-Atypical cells of undermined significance	-	02	02
4	L4-Suspiciousfor malignancy	-	03	03
5	L5- Malignant	Metastasis	02	09
		Metastatic Squamous Cell Carcinoma	02	
		Non-Hodgkin Lymphoma	03	
		Hodgkin Lymphoma	01	
		Leukemia infiltration	01	

Fig:1-Giemsa Stain Smear showing mixture of small and large lymphocytes, plasma cells and macrophages in the necrotic background – Reactive Lymphadenitis (100x)

Fig: 2 - Giemsa Stain Smear showing Large caseating necrosis and epithelioid cells with interspersed lymphoid cells–Granulomatous Lymphadenitis (400 x)

Fig:3 - Giemsa stain smear showing many scattered atypical keratinized cells with variable appearance, pleomorphic nuclei and high nucleocytoplasmic ratio with necrotic background–Metastatic Squamous

Fig:4 - Giemsa stain smear showing mixed population of small and large cells with neutrophils and eosinophils in the background with few Reedsternberg/Hodgkins cells- Hodgkin Lymphoma (50x)

Fig: 5 - FNAC Smear of non-Hodgkin's Lymphoma showing Monomorphic Population of Atypical Lymphoid cells with round nuclei (50x)

Discussion

The cytological evaluation of lymphadenopathies can be quite insightful. With the introduction of new auxiliary techniques and proper sample handling, combined with clinical data, diagnostic accuracy has significantly improved. To standardize the reporting of lymph node FNAC and assist in management, the Sydney system has been proposed.

The proposed Sydney system for the performance, diagnosis, and classification of lymph node cytopathology effectively addresses this need. Key features of this classification include recommendations for Rapid On-Site Evaluation (ROSE), suggestions for additional investigations at

a secondary diagnostic level, management guidelines for each category, and the calculation of the Risk of Malignancy (ROM) associated with each cytological diagnosis. In this study, the most common age group for lymph node cytology was 21 to 50 years, contrasting with those under 20 years in the study by Baruah AK et al. [17]. Male preponderance was noted [18]. Cervical lymph nodes were the most frequently sampled site for FNAC, followed by axillary nodes, consistent with findings in several other studies [17,18]. In the present study Male to female ratio was found to be 1.09:1 which is in accordance with the study done by Qadri SK et al. [19] & Mohanty R [20]. Gupta P et al., on evaluation of 6983 cases has found that

FNAC has high diagnostic accuracy, application of the Sydney system can help in achieving uniformity and reproducibility in cytologic diagnoses and help in risk-stratification [21]. Similar conclusions were drawn by Vigliar E et al. [22], and Joshee A and Joshee R (16) concluding that FNAC coupled with use of ancillary studies and implementation of Sydney system will be effective in evaluation of lymph node pathology. The present study showed the capability of the Sydney system to stratify lymph node FNACs into categories and calculate ROMs.

Conclusion

The newly proposed Sydney system for reporting lymph node cytopathology enhances diagnostic accuracy while ensuring uniformity and reproducibility in cytological diagnoses. It also helps bridge the communication gap between clinicians and pathologists, leading to improved patient management. Overall, the Sydney system effectively categorizes lymph node aspirates, resulting in more consistent reports and fostering better collaboration between cytopathologists and clinicians.

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